

TREE2U

Windows with increased dimensions using recovered wood

Circular design approach applied to wooden windows combines tradition and modern high tech to create distinct superior quality and long-life products.

Highlights of innovative features

- Recovered wood from characteristic historical building structures such as barns, mills, sheds, homesteads or hayracks is recycled into a modern, high-value product. Up to 30% recovery of wood from old structures can be achieved.
- Wood scantlings are complemented with a patented reinforcement system to redistribute load stress, enabling increased window dimensions of large span widths and up to 7m of height.
- Unique patina of reused wood can be used to add special and extraordinary identity and aesthetic value to the window product.
- Modular design approach and embedded smart sensors can prevent decay and prolong product life span.
- The company is developing a social app to improve wood recovery, by allowing users to send photos of excess or waste wood through the app allowing the company to decide if they will collect it.

The product helps raise consumer awareness for circular use in buildings. Large and slender windows optimize light transmission into built objects. Motorized windows integrate well into smart homes and can significantly enhance comfort and usability. The product is a prime example for a high-end circular and long-life product.

Company | Ownership of innovation

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